

DEVELOPMENT OF THE SPORTS BUILDING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *This article presents the management of a sports facility. It is presented how they should be developed and what is necessary for the development of sports facilities management systems.*

Keywords: *Significance of sports, athletes, sports facilities, system development, financial.*

Recently, sport has become an important branch of the economy of many countries, including Uzbekistan. New models of sports management and investments in it are constantly being improved and developed.

The recognition by the state of the importance of sports for society is expressed in its expanded investment, the constant increase in the number of sports facilities, the introduction of innovative methods and approaches both in the creation of sports facilities and in the management of sports.

At the same time, there is an acute shortage of sports facilities in most regions of Uzbekistan. This affects such fundamental criteria of the socio-economic system as life expectancy, deterioration of the main parameters of the nation's health, direct and indirect losses in the economy and society, lagging behind the sporting achievements of Uzbek athletes from athletes from other countries.

Currently, the development of sports infrastructure is a priority task of society and the state. In this regard, the formation of directions for the innovative development of sports infrastructure is relevant. An alternative to existing construction methods can only be technological innovations in the creation of sports facilities. The use of technological innovations in the construction and equipment of sports facilities will allow not only to develop and apply modern projects of sports complexes, but also significantly reduce construction costs, accelerate the process of construction of sports facilities, improve their quality, and, at the same time, increase the functionality and capacity of sports facilities.

The purpose of this study is to identify the main trends in the field of sports management of the highest achievements and to justify the need to reorganize the sports management system aimed at creating favorable conditions for sports, improving the level of training of high-class athletes, increasing the contribution of sports to the socio-

economic development of the country, which requires effective measures aimed at solving these tasks.

The analysis of modern trends in the field of sports management makes it possible to determine the most important vector of development, taking into account foreign experience and the specifics of Uzbek sports.

Among the heads of sports organizations, there is often an opinion that all the problems of sports development rest on insufficient funding, and they will automatically be solved if centralized financial allocations to the field of sports are increased. However, the experience of foreign countries shows that such expectations are unfounded. The decisive role in improving the sporting results of domestic athletes is associated, rather, with effective management than with an increase in financial revenues in this area.

The development of public administration in the field of sports should be done as follows:

- creation of corporate bodies with a large number of functions to expand the representation of all public and private interests in the field of sports.

- active use of innovative technologies and creation of multifunctional sports complexes;

- support and development of regional sports and mass sports events;

- organization of training of qualified sports managers;

- increasing the role of regional legislation, increasing regional intervention in the field of sponsorship of sports events, including the provision of broadcasts of sports competitions;

- creation of an effective management system for sports infrastructure facilities, tools to ensure effective public use of sports facilities;

- the emergence of comprehensive legislation in the field of sports.

Conclusion: The most important thing is to provide athletes with a place so that they can do well. And if they are provided with a beautiful, cozy place, then it even motivates them and it will be easy for them to achieve the goal.

REFERENCES:

1. Dobrynin A.S. Osnovnie tendencii v upravlenii razvitiem sporta visshix dostizhenii // Bulletin of the Altai Academy of Economics and Law. – 2019. – No. 9-1. – pp. 26-31;

2. Malyshev G.A. Innovacionnyy podxod k sovershenstvovaniyu infrastrukturi tennisnogo sporta /G.A. Malyshev // Transport business of Russia - 2010 - No. 2.

3. Malyshev G.A. Napravlenie sovershenstvovaniya innovacionnoy deyatel'nosti v sozdanii sportivnoy infrastruktury /G.A. Malyshev // UIID: Collection of scientific papers. Issue under the general editorship of A.Y. Egorov and M.V. Konotopov. - M.: GASIS 2007. (0,7 p.l.)